

ROLE OF WORKPLACE CONDITIONS IN INCOME OF WAGE EARNING AND SELF-EMPLOYED WOMEN IN THE INFORMAL SECTOR IN THE CITY OF TAJ: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS USING PROBIT MODEL

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Abstract: The quantum of income earned by working women is crucial to promote women empowerment. Good work place conditions can bring about changes in women's ability to earn better incomes. Using data from a primary survey of working women in the urban informal sector in the city of Taj, this paper constructed workplace condition index for both wage-earners and self-employed. An econometric analysis using probit model finds that better work place condition plays a significant role in improving the income of wage-earners and self-employed women. Also, the result shows that if a woman tries to find work near her home to balance household chore, then she actually compromises on income. Simultaneously, a better stable job and help from family members in completing household chores significantly increase her chances of earning high income.

Keywords: Work place condition, Income earned, Informal sector, Self-employed, Wage-earners

I Introduction

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Number 3 aims at promoting good health and wellbeing. According to Herzberg et al. (1959), workplace conditions are categorized into hygiene factors and motivators. The former includes factors like wages, working conditions, policies of the employer which can encourage or discourage the workers to work. Motivators, on the other hand, are related to the nature of the work itself and related to contributing to job satisfaction. Workplace conditions

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refer to the physical, social, and organizational environment in which work is performed. It can be defined as the circumstances such as working hours, stress, danger that affect the workplace (Kayode et al., 2018). This paper thus investigates whether women have access to better and good workplace conditions and whether better work place conditions have any role in enhancing the incomes earned by the women.

We did this by conducting a primary survey among working women in the urban informal sector in Agra city—the city of Taj. The paper is organized as follows. The next section reviews the literature on women's access to workplace conditions and their income-related empowerment. Section III describes the data and descriptive statistics. Section IV gives the estimation and the results. Section V gives concluding remarks and limitations.

II Literature Review

Women make up a disproportionately large component of the informal sector's working class, and they are engaged in a wide variety of jobs, from street vending and domestic help to subsistence farming and seasonal agricultural work. It is believed that over 94 percent of all working women in India are involved in the informal economy (Charmes, 2012; Mishra, 2023). Within the informal sector, women are generally found in low-income activity which barely guarantees survival. This is likely to be in self-employment or in casual or seasonal paid labour, often of an unskilled and physically demanding nature, with low productivity, long hours of engagement, and little opportunity for upward mobility or for acquiring or improving skills (Leach, 1996; Chakraborty, 2020). They do not come under workers welfare act, factory act, minimum wages act, and so on. They suffer a lot at their work places in the form of sexual harassment, seasonal employment, unfair wages and discriminatory practices (Nastiti et al., 2011; Williams and Horodnic, 2019).

Rantanen (2009) notes that the informal sector is often characterized by severe forms of exposure to hazards at the workplace. Devoid of social protection and pollution control measures, they suffer from risks of injuries and diseases (Adei et al., 2021). Women informal workers are at the bottom of labour-intensive global supply chains particularly in textiles, garments, leather and footwear and electronics. They earn low incomes, usually close to the poverty level (ILO, 2011). Instances of exploitative labour practices, including wage theft, forced overtime, and verbal and other abuses, are regrettably not uncommon in the informal sector. The vulnerable position of migrant women makes them susceptible to exploitation by employers who exploit their desperation for employment (Gupta, 2020).

Access to better workplace conditions can bring about changes in women workers' ability to earn higher incomes (Benach, 2007). Paramjit et al. (2023) have studied the impact of working conditions available to women at work on their income earned. In their study, they have looked into the women working only as wage earners in the three states of North India and found that access to good work conditions increases women's ability to earn higher income. In this paper, we study the relationship between work place conditions for working women (wage earner or self-employed) and the income earned by them, especially for the working women in the urban informal sector in the city of Taj.

Our contribution in the paper is the following. First, as just said, the study focuses not only on the wage earners but also the self-employed working women in the urban informal sector in the city of Taj. Second, the study has focused on one city to get a detailed understanding of the work place conditions for working women. The self-employed in this city have a very distinct characteristic. They do not do the conventional type of work and not assist their spouses in their work. They work

independently on their own. Third, some questions in our questionnaire attempt to capture the workplace conditions and classify them as positive or negative.

In this paper, we also examine whether providing women with assistance at home —help in cleaning, washing utensils, and child care—leads to higher income. We have tried to investigate if the presence of better work place conditions makes any difference in the income earned by the wage earners and the self-employed. The study also examines if distance from work place to home contributes positively to any change in the income earned. Against the above backdrop, this study seeks to find out issues related to inadequate workplace conditions of working women in urban informal sector. In this paper, the workplace condition (WPC) index has been constructed for better analysis. The methodology of construction of this index is similar to the one used by Besley-Burgess (BB) Index on labour regulation (Besley and Burgess, 2004). To the best of our knowledge, we have not come across any study which investigates the relationship between workplace condition and income.

III Data and Descriptive Statistics

The data for this study comes from a primary survey that we conducted among working women in the urban informal sector in Agra city. A structured questionnaire was used to get the requisite information. Apart from personal information of the respondent, the questionnaire has various sections, viz., occupational details, working conditions at work place, and economic empowerment of women, among others. Data was collected from March, 2023 to July, 2023. The survey was conducted in slums, colonies, factories, shops, different markets and other places in the urban informal sector, collecting information from 285 respondents. We did not consider activities like care-giving, tailoring, working in beauty parlours, household help, cleaners, washers, etc.; rather, special focus was given on wage employment and self-employment activities like handicraft (marble/wooden), *petha*/sweet making, shoe making, tourism, manufacturing of silver anklets and bracelets, *rakhi*, festoon and *poshak* making. In short, we considered those activities which require specialised skills. After reviewing, 219 responses were considered for the study.

The population of Agra as per the 2011 census has been recorded to be 4.418 million. The data suggest that leather industry and stone making consist of principal economic activities in Agra city. The lack of housing and basic services in and around these industries has resulted in the development of slums and squatter settlements with wider ramifications on the health, safety and well-being of the residents. Agra has 432 identified slums and other settlements without access to basic services and with poor environmental conditions. According to the Agra Master Plan 2021, these slums are distributed across 77 of 90 wards and seven planning zones of the city. Agra hosted the G20 EMPOWER Inception Meeting on the theme “Empowering Women to Lead across Sectors: Role of Digital Skilling and Future Skills” during 11-12 February 2023. We have 28 questions in the questionnaire to capture the conditions at work place of women. The questions are broadly divided in six categories and listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Working Condition for Wage Workers

Broad Indicators	Questions
Leave Conditions	1 Do you get compensation for working in an off day?
	2 Do you get paid leaves?
	3 Do you get weekly off?
	4 If you ever have to do overtime work, will you be paid for that?

Contd...

Table 1 contd...

Broad Indicators		Questions
	5	Can you leave early from work on some days?
	6	Do you get compensatory leave for coming on an off day?
	7	Do you get extra salary if you take less leave than prescribed?
	8	Do you get medical leaves?
	9	Do you get other leaves say maternity leaves?
“In kind” benefits received	10	Do you get “in kind” benefits in terms of free clothes?
	11	Do you get “in kind” benefits in terms of free food?
	12	Do you get any other “in kind” benefits?
Sanitation and hygiene	13	Is clean drinking water available at your workplace?
	14	Are clean toilets and sanitation facilities available at your workplace?
	15	Is separate place for having food available at your workplace?
Safety at workplace	16	Are machines and other equipment in good working conditions available at your workplace?
	17	Do you have electricity problems (tripping problems) at your workplace?
	18	Do you have use of hazardous chemicals at your workplace?
Physical and mental stress at workplace	19	Do you have noise (too loud) at your workplace?
	20	Do you do overtime work?
	21	Do you have exposure to extreme heat at your workplace?
	22	Do you suffer from uncomfortable work posture at your workplace?
	23	Do you handle heavy loads, usually more than the normal at your workplace?
	24	Do you suffer from abusive language by employer at your workplace?
	25	Do you suffer from long hours of standing (more than the normal) at your workplace?
Salary deduction at workplace	26	Is salary deducted if you leave early from work?
	27	Is salary deducted if you reach late to work?
	28	Is salary deducted if you take more than prescribed leaves in a month?

For women who mostly work at home or rent a place for themselves to do their work (for example, handicraft work, manufacturing of silver anklets and bracelets, *rakhi*, festoon and *poshak* making, etc. which require specialised skills), we have used a different set of variables to capture the conditions at work place. We have a total of nine variables which determine the condition at their work place, which is actually their home. The questions are broadly divided in four categories and listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Working Condition for Self-employed

Broad Indicators		Questions
Sanitation and Hygiene	1	Is there a clean washroom at your workplace?
	2	Is safe drinking water accessible to you at workplace?
Work related financial investment	3	Have you ever taken micro credit in your name?
	4	Do you decide about amount to be invested in business?

Contd...

Table 2 contd...

Broad Indicators		Questions
Harassment at workplace	5	Has there been any exposure to unfavourable weather conditions like extreme temperature, wind, rain, sun etc?
	6	Has there been any incident of imposition of fines?
	7	Do you face harassments from petty officials?
	8	Has there been any incident of confiscation of goods?
Working environment	9	Has there been any physical assault or the prospects of being hauled to court?

Though we agree that the questions listed in Table 1 and Table 2 may not fully capture the difference between employers' place and the place self-employed, these are however indicative in some way or the other. For example, though merely an employer is not blaming an employee for reaching late to work someday (Table 1), it may not guarantee that it is a positive indicator. Finally, if wages are not deducted for reaching late then it can benefit the worker. Thus, we consider the phenomenon of having reached late to work and hence deduction of her salary as a negative view of the employer towards the staff. It makes a woman worker constantly live under the threat of losing her job.

Women in the unorganized sector confront multiple adversities such as inequitable employment and income, inadequate maternity benefits, and increased susceptibility to sexual harassment (Singh and Kumari, 2024). In addition, women workers who are exposed to very high temperatures in their work place and inadequate sanitation facilities have significant risks of heat-related illnesses and urogenital issues (Venugopal et al., 2016). Informal sector is also characterized with problems of overtime and additional shifts, termination without pay or notice, unsafe working conditions, and lack of security for employees in the event of non-payment of wages (Sifullah et al., 2023).

The conditions at work place for both self-employed and wage earners are captured as a binary variable. For example, two categories of conditions at work place have been identified: Positive and Negative. Positive means good work place conditions, whereas negative means adverse work place conditions. While creating the work place condition index, positive variables are given +1. Of 28 variables listed in Table 1 for the women who are wage employees, 16 are positive, while 12 are negative. As regards these 16 questions, if the answer is 'Yes', it is assigned '1', else '0'. Similarly, to all the 12 negative variables, if the answer is 'Yes', it is assigned '1', else '0'.

The same exercise is done for the questions which were constructed for the self-employed. For self-employed women, we have a total of nine variables listed in Table 2, out of which four are positive, while 5 are negative. All are 0-1 type. Thus, work place condition index is created in the following manner: First, we created the work place condition positive index by adding all positive variables. Value 0 implies no access to that facility and 1 means that women have access to the facility. The higher the index value, the higher the access to the positive or the negative condition. Both positive and negative workplace condition indexes for wage earners and self-employed have been converted into a continuous index. Table 3 gives the description of the data and workplace condition index for various categories.

Majority women in the sample are in the age group of 25-45 years. The mean value of the workplace condition index rises with age and there is less variability in the index value for women increases and then decreases with the increase in age. This shows that with a rise in age, women become more stabilised in their jobs and have better negotiating capabilities. These women can demand access to good workplace conditions. The variability in access to good workplace conditions

first increases and then decreases with age. Initially, women have variations in their bargaining power depending on their family need. A woman with greater need is ready to work in poor condition. Women in the higher age group have access to better work place conditions.

Table 3: Work Place Condition Indices of Variable

	Variable	In Percentage Term	Working Condition Index			
			Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Age (years)	Upto 25	20	0.06	0.37	-0.76	0.64
	Upto 45	58	0.06	0.42	-1.3	0.82
	Above 45	22	0.11	0.38	-0.70	0.73
Education	Illiterate	15	0.08	0.42	-0.65	0.73
	Primary	39	0.01	0.44	-1.3	0.82
	Secondary	25	0.08	0.37	-1.10	0.67
	Above secondary	21	0.14	0.36	-0.95	0.73
Income Categories	Less than 10,000	68	0.04	0.39	-1.30	0.73
	10,000-20,000	21	0.16	0.41	-1.10	0.73
	More than 20,000	11	0.04	0.64	-0.95	0.82
Type of Employment	Wage Earners	83	0.18	0.30	-0.76	0.82
	Self- employed	17	-0.50	0.37	-1.30	0.30
Marital Status	Unmarried	15	15	0.32	-0.70	0.64
	Divorced	12	0.21	0.37	-0.65	0.73
	Married	68	0.05	0.41	-1.30	0.82
Religion	Hindus	72	0.087	-1.300	0.39	0.824
	Muslims	11	-0.13	0.46	-1.10	0.56
	Others	17	0.12	0.39	-0.65	0.67
Social Groups	SC/ST	41	0.05	0.40	-1.10	0.73
	General	44	0.10	0.39	-1.30	0.70
	OBC	15	0.03	0.43	-0.95	0.82
Household work	Help received	49	0.06	0.39	-1.30	0.82
	No help	51	0.08	0.41	-1.10	0.73
Staying with family	Yes staying	81	0.08	0.40	-1.30	0.82
	Not staying	19	0.03	0.39	-1.10	0.59
Distance	More than 2 kms	46	0.02	0.44	-1.30	0.82
	Upto 2 kms	54	0.11	0.36	-0.95	0.73

Source: Authors' calculations based on survey data

A large portion of women in the sample have primary level of education. Average value of workplace condition index rises from 'primary' to 'above secondary' level of education. This was expected. With the rise in the level of education, we may expect women to be more aware of their surroundings and to be demanding for better workplace (Acharya, 2008). The variability falls with the rise in education levels.

In our sample, 83 percent of women were working as wage earners and the rest as self-employed. The average workplace condition index is lower for the self-employed. The variability in access to better conditions increases for the self-employed. This was expected because acquiring better facilities at workplace—either work at home or work at a rented small place—involves a cost which has to be borne by the self-employed women themselves. This puts an extra financial burden on them and, therefore, most of the self-employed women compromise on workplace conditions to save cost. Only a few better-off women spend money for this. Hence there is large variation.

The average index value initially rises with the rise in income levels and then decreases. The results are as per our expectations. Variability is also behaving similarly across different income categories. This implies less bargaining power of lowest income category and as income goes up, some workers negotiate for improved workplace condition. However, there is a decline in range as we move to higher income category. This shows that the inequality in terms of availability of benefits mentioned in the form of positive and negative variables decreases with increase in income.

IV Estimation and Results

We find that apart from conditions at workplace, there are other factors that determine income earned by a woman in the informal sector. To determine this, we use the index of work place condition as the primary variable along with other control variables. The equation considered for regression is given as:

$$\text{Income}_i = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \text{WPCI}_i + \Theta_i \alpha_3' + \varepsilon_i$$

The dependent variable, i.e., income earned, has three categories which are ranked in increasing order. Thus, ordered probit model is used in estimating the above regression where the dependent variable takes values equal to 1, 2 and 3, respectively, for the three income categories: “Less than Rs. 10000”, “Rs. 10000–20000” and “Above Rs. 20000” per month, in the order of increasing rank.

WPCI_i is the work place condition index for the ith woman. It is an indicator of work place condition for the women working as wage earners or working as self-employed. Θ_i is a vector of control variables (whether a woman is a wage-earner or self-employed, her age, education level, marital status, religion, caste category, whether staying with family, whether she gets help in household work and distance of workplace from her home). We have included all these variables in the model because income earned by women is not just affected by the conditions at work place, but is also influenced by these factors.

We want to find out the marginal effect of all the variables on the right-hand side of the equation. Since the main variable of interest is the work place condition index, we have considered two models of regression. In model 1, work place condition index and the control variables are considered as individual explanatory variables. In model 2, in addition, we have included an interaction variable, which is the multiplication between wage earner and working condition index. This interaction variable tries to capture the impact of work place condition on income for wage earners.

Robustness Check

Table 4 gives the estimation results. Each of the three outcomes, that is lowest, middle and highest income categories have two models each. Model 1 does not take into account the interaction term, whereas Model 2 does. In each outcome, i.e., outcome I, outcome II and outcome III in Table 4, gives the marginal effects from the probit regressions of the three categories of income levels.

Table 4: Estimation Results for Income Earned

	Outcome I (Lowest Income Category)					
	Model 1			Model 2		
	Income order = 1, Prob = 0.8106			Income order = 1, Prob = 0.8211		
	dy /dx	Std. error	P value	dy /dx	Std. error	P value
Wage worker	0.187	0.125	0.135	-0.005	0.122	0.966
BBIndex	-0.198	0.090	0.028	0.147	0.194	0.448
Age	-0.001	0.003	0.857	-0.001	0.003	0.656
Divorced	-0.034	0.132	0.797	0.015	0.112	0.891
Married	-0.023	0.081	0.778	0.009	0.080	0.910
Hindu	0.101	0.075	0.176	0.099	0.073	0.174
Muslim	0.121	0.074	0.101	0.117	0.075	0.117
General	-0.130	0.070	0.064	-0.123	0.070	0.078
OBC	-0.285	0.117	0.015	-0.298	0.118	0.012
Primary	-0.220	0.118	0.063	-0.236	0.121	0.051
Secondary	-0.238	0.137	0.083	-0.266	0.142	0.060
Above secondary	-0.361	0.150	0.016	-0.394	0.152	0.010
Stays with family	-0.083	0.059	0.157	-0.079	0.057	0.166
Migration	-0.180	0.060	0.003	-0.184	0.059	0.002
Working hours per day	0.033	0.021	0.108	0.032	0.019	0.095
No. of days working in a month	-0.016	0.009	0.084	-0.015	0.010	0.126
Family helps her in household work	-0.056	0.057	0.324	-0.065	0.055	0.242
Distance between workplace and home is up to 2 kms	0.124	0.057	0.030	0.122	0.057	0.032
Wage worker*BBIndex	NA	NA	NA	-0.047	0.210	0.030

	Outcome II (Middle Income Category)					
	Model 1			Model 2		
	Income order = 2, Prob = 0.1790			Income order = 1, Prob = 0.1702		
	dy /dx	Std. error	P value	dy /dx	Std. error	P value
Wage worker	-0.160	0.103	0.120	0.005	0.111	0.966
BBIndex	0.178	0.085	0.036	-0.134	0.176	0.447
Age	0.001	0.003	0.857	0.001	0.003	0.657
Divorced	0.030	0.116	0.795	-0.014	0.103	0.891
Married	0.020	0.073	0.778	-0.008	0.072	0.910
Hindu	-0.089	0.066	0.175	-0.089	0.065	0.173
Muslim	0.112	0.070	0.110	-0.109	0.071	0.125
General	0.115	0.064	0.070	0.111	0.064	0.082
OBC	0.235	0.088	0.007	0.249	0.090	0.006
Primary	0.191	0.100	0.057	0.206	0.103	0.045
Secondary	0.204	0.111	0.067	0.230	0.115	0.046
Above secondary	0.293	0.107	0.006	0.322	0.108	0.003
Stays with family	0.076	0.055	0.168	0.072	0.053	0.175
Migration	0.159	0.053	0.003	-0.164	0.052	0.002
Working hours per day	-0.030	0.019	0.109	-0.029	0.018	0.097
No. of days working in a month	0.015	0.009	0.089	0.014	0.009	0.128

Contd..

Table 4 contd...

Outcome II (Middle Income Category)						
	Model 1			Model 2		
	Income order = 2, Prob = 0.1790			Income order = 1, Prob = 0.1702		
	dy /dx	Std. error	P value	dy /dx	Std. error	P value
Family helps her in household work	0.051	0.051	0.320	0.059	0.050	0.239
Distance between workplace and home is up to 2 kms	-0.111	0.050	0.027	-0.110	0.050	0.029
Wage worker*BBindex	NA	NA	NA	0.416	0.193	0.032
Outcome III (Highest Income Category)						
	Model 1			Model 2		
	Income order = 3, Prob = 0.0104			Income order = 3, Prob = 0.0087		
	dy /dx	Std. error	P value	dy /dx	Std. error	P value
Wage worker	-0.027	0.025	0.274	0.001	0.011	0.966
BBIndex	0.020	0.010	0.041	-0.013	0.019	0.483
Age	0.001	0.001	0.857	0.002	0.000	0.656
Divorced	0.004	0.016	0.817	-0.001	0.009	0.885
Married	0.002	0.008	0.780	-0.001	0.007	0.910
Hindu	-0.012	0.010	0.246	-0.010	0.009	0.246
Muslim	-0.010	0.006	0.118	-0.008	0.005	0.123
General	0.014	0.009	0.095	0.012	0.008	0.118
OBC	0.050	0.036	0.161	0.049	0.034	0.155
Primary	0.029	0.022	0.176	0.029	0.021	0.173
Secondary	0.034	0.029	0.246	0.036	0.030	0.236
Above secondary	0.068	0.050	0.179	0.072	0.053	0.170
Stays with family	0.007	0.005	0.141	0.006	0.004	0.159
Migration	0.021	0.011	0.056	0.020	0.011	0.068
Working hours per day	-0.003	0.003	0.186	-0.003	0.002	0.160
No. of days working in a month	0.002	0.001	0.131	0.001	0.001	0.187
Family helps her in household work	0.006	0.007	0.390	0.006	0.006	0.322
Distance between workplace and home is up to 2 kms	-0.013	0.009	0.142	-0.012	0.008	0.157
Wage worker*BBindex	NA	NA	NA	0.041	0.025	0.089

Notes: BBIndex is the Besley Burgess Index. Wage worker*BBindex is the interaction term, i.e., product between wage employed and working condition index. Base Categories: illiterate, unmarried, other religion, not staying with family, no household work help at home, not migrated, self-employed, distance to workplace more than 2 kms.

Source: Authors' calculations based on survey data.

The probability of income earned in the lowest income slab witnesses a fall with the rise in the workplace condition index, whereas the likelihood of income earned in the middle and the highest income slabs increases with the rise in workplace condition index. These were expected. For wage earners, if the employer gives more benefit to the employees in the form of better workplace conditions, the efficiency of workers increases. The conditions under which most informal workers operate are precarious and unsafe. Many of the micro-enterprises in which they operate have ramshackle structures, lack sanitary facilities or potable water and have poor waste disposals (Forastieri, 1999). The poor nature of the working environment of the informal sector poses risks

of injuries and diseases to workers, thereby undermining their health and well-being (Adei et al., 2021). Poor health can affect individual and social welfare by reducing earning capacity and hours worked, especially for informal workers in low- and middle-income countries (Sarker et al., 2016). In small firms, employee absenteeism results in lower productivity and wages (Zhang et al., 2017). Organizational attempts to a convenient and safe physical environment improve work performance (Grant et al., 2019; Jinnett et al., 2017). When living and working conditions of female informal workers improve, so does their productivity, which leads to increased income (Bertulfo, 2011).

With the improvement in workplace conditions, there is a probability of rise in income for both the middle- and higher-income categories, but the probability falls for the lowest income category. These results become insignificant in model II when we include an extra variable, i.e., the interaction of the wage earners with the workplace conditions index. The workplace condition index is significant on its own but its role becomes insignificant if we include the interaction of workplace condition and the wage earners. This is because workplace condition matters more for wage workers as compared to self-employed workers. Self-employment is driven by labour market forces, such as unemployment and poor working conditions in wage employment sectors, that compel workers to seek alternative income opportunities, along with other supplementary benefits such as autonomy, work-life balance, etc. (Huang et al., 2020). Female workers engaged in informal sector in our sample work in their own dwelling. Hence, workplace condition for them is self-administered, whereas workplace condition for wage workers depends on employer. The better the workplace condition, the lower the likelihood of a wage worker being absent from work. Improvements in the work environment will reduce the negative health effects on the current workers and therefore lower absenteeism (Ose, 2005).

The probability of income earned in the lowest income category increases for wage employed women, whereas it witnesses a fall in the middle- and high-income categories. Within the informal sector, women earn a relatively lower wage than men and their engagement is more visible in the 'lower-value-added' activities of the informal economy (Ramani et al., 2013). Most of the women workers lack proper training. They have very few options to avail so far as gainful jobs are concerned. Women workers engaged in the informal sector are poor (perhaps poorest of the poor) uneducated and weak (Goel et al., 2011).

With increase in the age of women, there is a probability of fall in income (although insignificant) in the lowest income category and there is a probability of rise in income (although insignificant) in the rest of the income categories. The progression of age is often associated with the accumulation of experience and knowledge that can enhance income potential. This suggests that as the age of the worker increases, the likelihood of earning a decent income also increases (Syafitri et al., 2023).

The results also show that with a rise in the level of education, the probability of women's engagement in the lowest income category falls significantly in both the models, whereas it rises in the middle- and higher-income categories. This is because in the informal sector the higher income segments have higher returns to education (Unni, 2023).

For marital status we get mixed results. Probability of earning higher income by the lowest income category falls in model 1 but rises in model 2 but both the results are statistically insignificant. The probability of earning higher income by the middle income category increases insignificantly in model 1, whereas it falls insignificantly in model 2. It is only in the highest income category that the probability rises significantly in model 1. The explanation follows Pilossoph and Wee (2021) who argue that the marriage wage premium is driven by income pooling and improved job matching within a household. By sharing finances, married individuals increase their reservation wages and

climb the job ladder faster to secure higher pay. A higher reservation wage implies a willingness to wait for higher-paying jobs. Married individuals have an extra incentive to climb the job ladder, i.e., to look for better opportunities while employed.

For women staying with families, we get mixed results. The probability of earning falls for the low income category and it rises for the middle- and higher-income categories; but the results are statistically insignificant. The family's needs for basic materials are getting bigger and bigger with time. There is no other way but to require women to supplement the family income (Zunaidi et al., 2021). We got mixed results for wage earners in both the models for all the income categories. Wage earners are more likely to be in the lowest income category rather than in middle- or highest-income categories. However, all the results are statistically insignificant.

The probability of women to earn income rises significantly for the lowest income category, if women stay near their workplace, whereas it falls significantly for the higher income category. This shows that distance plays an important role for the low income group, as women do not want to spend a lot of time on commuting. Informal jobs offer certain appealing features such as the opportunity to be employed closer to home and greater flexibility, which helps a woman to maintain work-life balance (Malta et al., 2019).

With a rise in the number of working days per month for the low income category, a significant fall is seen in the probability of women to be earning an income. This shows that women do not tend to work more, unless they are paid for it. They earn higher incomes with the rise in number of working days although this result is statistically insignificant. Limited working hours combined with precarious earnings results in a high incidence of under-employment in informal work. This drives informal workers to seek other employment or work for more days in a month to increase earnings (Nath et al., 2023). The probability of earning an income is higher for both Hindu and Muslim women belonging to the low income category. In the similar line, other results are self-explanatory.

V Discussion and Concluding Remarks

Our paper shows that if working condition can be improved in the informal sector then women will become more productive and they will earn higher income which can empower them financially. The likelihood of women earning a higher income in the middle- and highest-income categories increases and the probability of them being in the lowest category of income decreases with the improvement in workplace conditions. This is true for all women working in the informal sector, irrespective of a wage-earner or self-employed. The paper also establishes that distance of workplace plays an important role in women's income. Burden of home responsibilities often compels a woman to search for jobs which are available close to their home but this implies sacrificing opportunity of earning higher income. If her workplace is a bit away from her home, then her probability of earning higher income increases. Finally, if family members help her in household chores then her chance of earning higher income increases.

A number of women welfare schemes have been initiated by the Government of India, such as PM SVANidhi (a collateral free micro-credit scheme for urban street vendors to help them restart and grow), Pradhan Mantri Shram Yogi Maan-dhan (PM-SYM) (a voluntary and contributory pension scheme for unorganized sector workers), and Prime Minister Awas Yojana Urban (PMAY-U) scheme (housing assistance for the urban poor), among others. Also, the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare has introduced a scheme for promotion of menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls. However, the system often fails to properly address the issues of health, safety, and productivity of women, and to advance gender equity more broadly. There should be a monitoring

system to check whether the implementation of the various welfare measures is quickly and more efficiently done so that the benefits reach the masses without any time gap.

We accept that there could be various limitations in our study. One, we do acknowledge that due to logistical reasons, the sample size of the study for the self-employed women is small. However, there is much heterogeneity in the sample. Two, we do not cover male perspectives in the analysis. We have only surveyed females in our survey. If we would have surveyed husbands and/or fathers of women (wherever applicable), then it would have helped us to find out gender gap in income earned and the factors determining this gender gap. We hope to overcome these shortcomings in future research work.

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References

- Acharya, Y. (2008), “Women’s Education and Intra-household Autonomy: Evidence from Nepal”, *Journal of Development and Social Transformation*, 5.
- Adei, D., I. Braimah, J.V. Mensah, A.A. Mensah and W.A. Duah (2021), “Improving upon the Working Environment”, *Cogent Medicine*, 8.
- Benach, J., C. Muntaner and V. Santana (2007), “Employment Conditions and Health Inequalities”, Employment Conditions Knowledge Network (EMCONET). Final Report, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>.
- Bertulfo, L. (2011), “Women and the Informal Economy”, Office of Development Effectiveness, Australian Government.
- Besley, T. and R. Burgess (2004), “Can Regulation Hinder Economic Performance? Evidence from India”, *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 119(1): 91-134.
- Chakraborty, S. (2020), “COVID-19 and Women Informal Sector Workers in India”, *Economic and Political Weekly*, 55(35): 17-21.
- Charmes, J. (2012), “The Informal Economy Worldwide: Trends and Characteristics”, *Margin: The Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 6(2): 103-132.
- Forastieri, V. (1999), “Improvement of Working Conditions and Environment in the Informal Sector through Safety and Health Measures”, International Labour Office.
- Grant, A.M., S.A. O’Connor and I. Studholme (2019), “Towards a Positive Psychology of Buildings and Workplace Community: The Positive Built Workplace Environment”, *International Journal of Applied Positive Psychology*, 4(1-2): 67-89.
- Goel, G., T. Singh and A. Gupta (2011), “Women Working in Informal Sector in India: A Saga of Lopsided Utilization of Human Capital”, *International Conference on Economics and Finance Research*. 4: 534-538.
- Gupta, S. (2020), “Exploitation of Migrant Women in the Informal Labour Sector”, *Journal of Exploitation Studies*, 15(2): 45-57.
- Herzberg, F., B. Mausner and B.B. Snyderman (1959), *The Motivation to Work*, John Wiley & Sons.

- Huang, G., D. Xue, Y. Guo and C. Wang (2020), “Constrained Voluntary Informalisation: Analysing Motivations of Self-employed Migrant Workers in an Urban Village, Guangzhou”, *Cities*, 10: 1-10.
- ILO (2011), “World of Work Report 2011: Making Markets Work for Jobs”, International Labour Office, Geneva.
- Jinnett, K., N. Schwatka, L. Tenney, C.v.S. Brockbank and L.S. Newman (2017), “Chronic Conditions, Workplace Safety, and Job Demands Contribute to Absenteeism and Job Performance”, *Health Affairs*, 36(2): 237-244.
- Kayode, A., O. Christianah, Adegbenro., A. Caleb, A. Akinpelu., A. Oladayo, A., Ayeni., A. Raphael, F. Oluwafunmilola and Monehin and Samuel (2018), “Poor Work Environment: A Barrier to Efficiency in Healthcare Delivery Services (A Study Conducted at Federal Medical Centre, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria)”, *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 6(5): 480-487.
- Leach, F. (1996), “Women in the Informal Sector: The Contribution of Education and Training”, *Development in Practice*, 6(1): 25-36.
- Malta, V., L. Kolovich, A.M. Leyva and M.M. Tavares (2019). “Informality and Gender Gaps Going Hand in Hand”, *IMF Working Paper*.
- Mishra, A. (2023), “Women on the Verge: Marginalising Female Workforce in the Indian Informal Economy”, *ESSBC Journal of Business Studies*, 1(1): 35-44.
- Nastiti, A., I. Prabaharyaka, D. Roosmini and T.D. Kunaefi (2011), “Health-associated Cost of Urban Informal Industrial Sector: An Assessment Tool”, *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 36: 112-122.
- Nath, P., S.N. Mandela and A. Gawali (2023), “Loss, Recovery and the Long Road Ahead: Tracking India’s Informal Workers through the Pandemic”, *Indian Journal of Labour Economics*, 66: 329-354.
- Ose, S.O. (2005), “Working Conditions, Compensation and Absenteeism”, *Journal of Health Economics*, 24: 161-188.
- Paramjit, S. Goel, A. Gupta and S. Singh (2023), “Determinants of Income Earned by Women Working in the Urban Informal Sector in India: An Empirical Study”, *Anvesak*, 53(2): 72-86.
- Pilosoph, L. and S.L. Wee (2021), “Household Search and the Marital Wage Premium”, *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 13(4): 55-109.
- Ramani, S.V., A. Thutupalli, T. Medovarszki, S. Chattopadhyay and V. Ravichandran (2013), “Women in the Informal Economy: Experiments in Governance from Emerging Countries”, Policy Brief, United Nations University.
- Rantanen, J. (2009), “Occupational Health Services for the Informal Sector”, *African Newsletter on Occupational Health and Safety*, 19(2): 44-46.
- Sarker, A.R., M. Sultana, R.A. Mahumud, S. Ahmed, M.W. Ahmed, M.E. Hoque, Z. Islam, R. Gazi and J.A.M. Khan (2016), “Effects of Occupational Illness on Labor Productivity: A Socioeconomic Aspect of Informal Sector Workers in Urban Bangladesh”, *Journal of Occupational Health*, 58: 209-215.
- Sifullah, M.K., M.S. Sohel, M.F.H. Sarker, M. Islam, M. Ahmad and M.M. Rahman (2023), “Mapping out the Vulnerabilities of Migrant Women in the Informal Sector: A Qualitative Investigation in Dhaka City”, *Helijon*, 9: 1-15.
- Singh, S.A. and A. Kumari (2024), “Challenges and Opportunities: Women’s Working Conditions in India’s Unorganized Sector”. SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4714308>.

- Syafitri, W., B. Fitanto, A.M. Setyanti and N. Izza (2023), "Income Determinants of Women in East Java's Informal Labor Market: Microdata Approach", *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Humaniora*, 12(3): 582-592.
- Unni, J. (2023), "Private Investment in Education and Linkage to Future Employment in India: Will the Pandemic Take its Toll?", *Indian Journal of Labour Economics*, 66: 267-281.
- Venugopal, V., S. Rekha, K. Manikandan, P.K. Latha, V. Vennila, N. Ganesan, P. Kumaravel and S.J. Chinnadurai (2016), "Heat Stress and Inadequate Sanitary Facilities at Workplaces an Occupational Health Concern for Women?", *Global Health Action*, 9(1).
- Williams, C.C. and I.A. Horodnic (2019), "Evaluating Working Conditions in the Informal Economy: Evidence from the 2015 European Working Conditions Survey", *International Sociology*, 34(3): 281-306.
- Zhang, W., H. Sun, S. Woodcock and A.H. Anis (2017), "Valuing Productivity Loss due to Absenteeism: Firm-level Evidence from a Canadian linked Employer-employee Survey", *Health Economics Review*, 7(3): 2-14.
- Zunaidi, A., and F.L. Maghfiroh (2021), "The Role of Women in Improving the Family Economy", *Islamic Economics & Financial Journal*, 8(1): 61-79.